

The relationship of the temple economy of Ugarit relating to the fall of the City State (scrapped)

To John Huehnergard, who authored the first research on the Ancient Near East I had ever done.

Introduction:

Ugarit was a city-state flourishing around the 2nd millennium BCE, around 10km North of modern-day Latakia, discovered around the spring of 1928. Since then, it has not only captured the minds of Assyriologists but created a more niche sector of Assyriology (the study of the ancient civilizations of Mesopotamia), Ugaritology (the study of the coastal city-state of Ugarit). Being occupied since the Neolithic period (specifically the 7th millennium BCE), it had flourished around circa the 2nd millennium BCE and had fallen in around 1200 BCE-1180 BCE from a fire and had never been recovered. Since this discovery, scholars have largely come to a consensus on the external factors which directly caused the fall of Ugarit. In fact, to many, Ugarit's fall is still based on factors such as severe drought and famine. However, many may have overlooked the internal factors, which, in turn, may or may not have amplified its fall. Since much of the economic production of Ugarit was towards the temple and its rituals ¹, the question arises: could the religious economy (specifically the ritual factors of the cult) of the city-state amplify strain on the already present famine and economic failure of the city?

Analysis:

In what comes forward, I should try to explain and conclude on some of the features of the temple economy which may or may not contribute to the question of “could

¹ Watson and Wyatt, 1999

the religious economy of the city state amplify strain on the already present economic failure of the city?”. Due to the large undertaking of this topic, I shall restrict myself to a few points. The points being:

1. An overview on the principles and basic theology of the religion of Ugarit.
2. The temple as an Institutional and Economic Center
3. How the temple economy may have functioned.
4. How ritual sacrifices may have impacted the economical production of Ugarit
5. Conclusion

1. Principles and basic theology of the religion of Ugarit

In the Ugaritic religion, there are two types of texts mythological/literary, and cultic. Mythological texts present a “theological universe and its pantheon” and helps express a system of ideas in which explain the fundamental and metaphysical questions of life for the religious.² The cultic texts presenting a more “functional” side of the religion, which in this case calls the religious to take action in a variety of mannerisms (that being monthly liturgies, divinatory texts and oracles, prayers, incantations, expiatory sacrifices, liturgies for kings, votive texts, and list of Gods).³ It is also known that the official temple had to follow much stricter rules and customs compared to the fluidity and personal piety in the

² Del Olmo Lete, 2014

³ Xella, 1981, as reviewed by Segert, 1982

Ugaritic Religion. The ritual and mythological texts show the great complexity of the Religion and theology of Ugarit.

In Ugaritic religion, texts like the Baalu-Anatu cycle and other mythological were the work of a “storyteller” and was passed orally than later recorded⁴ (specifically by Ilimilku)⁵, we also recognize that out of the many gods (240), very few actually do anything, with around 8 principle gods appearing in the Baalu-Anatu cycle, 6 less important gods which appear in less important mythological texts, and 24 who are merely mentioned/inactive.⁶ Genealogically, it is known that all the Gods stem from one primordial couple, Ilu, and Athiratu, with Ilu having sonship over all gods, whether collectively or individually⁷, hence, the “sons of Ilu” or bn ilm (with the texts reinforcing this by calling mythological protagonists such as Keret “son(s) of Ilu”^{8 9} with no “younger” gods overtaking the Primordial Couple. Ilu also assumes the “creator” role, or to better put it the “father of mankind” (ab adm).^{10 11} It is also known that Ilu is of “advanced age” (ab šnm), or a simpler way to put it, he is quite an old god.¹² This “generic” sonship and the fact that no younger gods overtake the primordial couple is an influential part of Ugaritic theology very present in the Baalu-Anatu cycle and many other myths.

The Baalu-Anatu cycle (KTU 1.1-1.6) speaks on the fight for pre-eminence under the god Ilu between three “principal deities” (that being Yammu, the god of the Sea, Môtû, the

⁴ Kawashima, 2020

⁵ Smith, 2008

⁶ Del Olmo Lete, 2014

⁷ Xella, 2015

⁸ KTU 1.14

⁹ Xella, 2015

¹⁰ KTU 1.14

¹¹ Xella, 2015

¹² Smith, 1994, as reviewed by Segert, 1996

god of the underworld and Baalu, the storm god).¹³ The story, which is heavily dependent on seasonal cycles,¹⁴ is believed to be according to Robert S. Kawashima, a narrative that moves from a time of “cosmic strife” to a time of “cosmic unification”.¹⁵ As we are presented by the mythological text, we can deduce two existing groups, the family of Ilu, and the assembly of Baalu (Presented in KTU 1:39)¹⁶. Since the evidence for the entire story is fragmentary, the Mark Smith ordering of the tablets will be followed: KTU 1.1-1.2, describes the battle between Baalu and Yammu, ending with Yammu’s death, as for KTU 1.3-1.4, this describes the quest for the palace of Baalu, with the final tablets (KTU 1.5-1.6), describing the battle with Môtû and Baalu, leading to the eventual victory of Baalu.¹⁷ These texts also present Baalu as the protagonist¹⁸, this of course, is reinforced by the importance of rain in the geographical area of the ancient city-state.¹⁹ This cycle is extremely important and fundamental toward the mythological pantheon of Ugarit, its cosmic universe, and ritual/cultic proceedings.

While the mythological pantheon is important, the liturgical pantheon is of equal or greater importance. These mythological pantheons, though uncoordinated in relation to the hierarchy of the deities in their list of deities²⁰, these liturgical pantheons provide the path for understanding the official Ugaritic cultic practices and beliefs. One very important pantheon relating to the public liturgy is the pantheon of the king or dynasty. As it is known that the king was very much present in public liturgy and cultic rites. Not only this, but

¹³ Gibson, 1984

¹⁴ Del Olmo Lete, 2014

¹⁵ Kawashima, 2020

¹⁶ Del Olmo Lete, 2014

¹⁷ Smith, 2008

¹⁸ Smith, 1994, as reviewed by Pardee, 1998

¹⁹ Del Olmo Lete, 2014

²⁰ Del Olmo Lete, 2014

many rituals took place in the palace, primarily in the chapel area.²¹ While the list of Gods in the king's pantheon is without a standard list, we can deduct these 3 types, 1. Ones that are specifically special to the king 2. Ones that are directly involved or connected with the palace 3. Ones of the "ancestor" cult in Ugarit.²² Finally, it is also known that defied kings were perceived as Gods.²³ This information helps us understand this specific pantheon and its importance in public liturgy and perception.

While mythological texts are important to the theology of Ugarit and its principles, they form the more mainstream pantheon and are used to solve fundamental and metaphysical questions from the religious, as discussed before in the introductory paragraph of my first point/undertaking. With the discussion of the mythological text ending around the description of the Baalu-Anatu cycle and a transition into more of a ritual pantheon and theology with the synthesis of the Pantheon of the King. In these next paragraphs, I will use the current theological principles and apply it to cultic texts and its pantheon, with a slight economical focus on the rituals described. I will also begin to present again the current "idea" of what the cultic texts are and how they differ from the mythological texts. Which, in turn, will later help us pivot towards the economical focus of the temple and how it may or may not have amplified the fall of the city state.

In Ugaritic religion, ritual texts, act as a more "functional part" of religious life²⁴, which can be divided into two ritual groups "sacrificial rituals" and "non sacrificial

²¹ Watson and Wyatt, 1999

²² Del Olmo Lete, 2014

²³ Watson and Wyatt, 1999

²⁴ Del Olmo Lete, 2014

liturgies”²⁵, but the text themselves can be split into 8 types, with the exact hierarchy being used depending on textual amount and coverage (the types being, 1. monthly liturgies and offering lists 2. divinatory Texts and oracles, 3. prayers and incantations, 4. atonement sacrifices, 5. liturgies for kings, votive texts, and God lists) ²⁶. According to textual evidence it is known that while the king was directly involved with public liturgy, there is no mention of “khn̄m” (priests) or “br khn̄m” (chief priest) in ritual texts, with the only available information on these other roles found in economic or administrative texts.²⁷ This section will be divided into two smaller subgroups, that being the analyzing of the pantheons and theological principles of sacrificial rituals and non-sacrificial rites. This will benefit the journal as it will not only make the argument clearer but help with the focus on the specific pantheon without jumping between topics.

1. The pantheon and types of Sacrificial Rituals.

Sacrificial rituals are the main type of ritual at the time, shown with heavy amounts of textual coverage.²⁸ In sacrificial rituals, it is known that a type of plan was given, detailing the methods, offering, and Gods who are receiving such an Offering. ²⁹ Scholars note that sacrificial rituals are placed into two greater detailed subgroups, prescribed, and described, which divide the “sacrificial” corpus of tablets in Ugarit.³⁰ With prescribed texts describing the mannerism and techniques to perform the rituals, and described texts, essentially “describing” what happens in each ritual (that being the sequence of sacrifices to many gods

²⁵ Del Olmo Lete, 2014 talks deeply about the two types, with a section allotted for each type.

²⁶ Xella, 1981, as reviewed by Segert, 1982

²⁷ Watson and Wyatt, 1999

²⁸ Xella, 1981, as reviewed by Segert, 1982

²⁹ Del Olmo Lete, 2014

³⁰ Watson and Wyatt, 1999

and the rites that go with it).³¹ Descriptive texts, primarily characterized by Baruch A. Levine, are formulaic texts rather than prosaic, with formulae such as item to the deity, and deity to the item.³² It is also recognized that Ugaritic cultic procedures also found invaluable certain classification of animals in (whether by sex, class, and genus) depending on text, with evidence such as words like “alp” (head of a large cattle), and “Imr” (sheep).³³ Baruch A. Levine also speaks on a very well-known topic in the study of Ugaritic Public Liturgy, that being kings, as he highlights the use of kings in public liturgy by explaining the use of the word “mlk” (meaning king), in the text of KTU 1.39, affirming the use of kings in public liturgy, which has been reflected and talked about by many scholars in the field.³⁴

In Ugaritic public liturgy, prescriptive texts serve as one of the “pillars” of sacrificial rituals. Prescriptive rituals, which are also formulaic rather than prosaic³⁵, detail the mannerism and technique of the ritual, compared to descriptive rituals in which essentially “describe” the ritual at hand.³⁶ While the language of ritual texts is still quite debated in terms of parsing, major impacts such as DULAT (A Dictionary of the Ugaritic Language in the Alphabetic Tradition) made by leading scholars Gregorio del Olmo Lete and Joaquín Sanmartín, helping to give an insight into the Ugaritic ritual lexicon, and Dennis

³¹ Levine, 2011

³² These specific formulae are observed by Levine, 2011, the texts being KTU 1.39, 1.40, and 1.41.

³³ Levine, 2011

³⁴ Such scholars being Levine, as previously mentioned, also Watson and Wyatt in the 1999 Ugaritic Handbook, and scholar Del Olmo Lete in the work Canaanite texts according to the liturgical texts of Ugarit, 2014

³⁵ Watson and Wyatt, 1999

³⁶ Levine, 2011

Pardee's work "Ritual and Cult at Ugarit", which helps translate and parse Ugaritic ritual texts. Though undoubtedly invaluable, some scholars such as Baruch A Levine parse some tablets differently, but the main translation and parsing of the tablets will be by the scholar Dennis Pardee, as I believe that Baruch A Levine's work on Ugaritic tablet translation gives less comprehensible meanings. In specific, it is known that Ugaritic Prescriptive rituals have an implicit or explicit time frame, with some monthly, and others covering a shorter period.³⁷ With these prescriptive rituals, we will analyze 3 tablets, (that being, RS 1.009, RS 24.253, RS 24.284), which has a month never indicated in them, or of course it may have been lost.³⁸ In our first tablet analyzed (RS 1.009), a formulaic expression can be analyzed, like the descriptive formulas (Name of Item – Deity), which is found in line three of the tablet (š. I`l š. b`l š. dgn š.), with š defining a male of the flock or a ram,³⁹ and I`l defining Ilu, B`l defining Baalu, and Dgn defining Daganu,⁴⁰ which, translating means "for Ilu a ram, for Baalu a ram, for Daganu a ram". The king is also described in the ritual tablets and relates to the importance of the king in public liturgy, with tablet RS 24.253, saying "ytrhs.mlk.brr" (the king will watch himself clean)⁴¹, and heavy economical use, which is one of the amplifying factors which causes scholars to believe the temple to be an economical and institutional powerhouse.⁴²

2. Non sacrificial rites

³⁷ Pardee, 2002

³⁸ Pardee, 2002

³⁹ Levine, 2011

⁴⁰ Del Olmo Lete, 2014

⁴¹ Pardee, 2002

⁴² Watson and Wyatt, 1999

